

Estimation of Target Signatures for High-Resolution Through-the-Wall Imaging: Computational Complexity Analysis

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Abstract. High-resolution through-the-wall radar imaging (TWRI) is a formidable challenge in a cluttered and dynamic environment, because strong wall returns often overwhelm the weaker echoes from targets. Indoor clutter and dense multipath further blur fine spatial details and complicate target discrimination. These challenges demand computationally efficient imaging algorithms to preserve high-resolution performance in real operational settings. This research work investigates the trade-offs between computational complexity and estimation accuracy for high-resolution through-the-wall image reconstruction. This paper develops a multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) virtual array framework that synthesizes a large aperture to improve spatial resolution. It presents a hybrid image reconstruction (HIR) technique that integrates FFT-based processing with subspace-based spectral estimation. The proposed hybrid methodology exploits the efficiency of FFT for coarse focusing and the high resolution of MUSIC for fine imaging. The objective of this hybrid approach is to achieve superior image reconstruction compared with 3D-FFT, range migration algorithm (RMA) and conventional beamforming (CBF) approaches. A systematic system model and analytical formulation of the proposed methodology is presented. This paper also presents a comprehensive stepwise computational complexity derivation and analysis for the proposed methodology alongwith the 3D-FFT and RMA imaging techniques. The analysis provides quantitative insight into the trade-offs between estimation accuracy, angular resolution and computational burden. Comprehensive analytical and numerical performance evaluation highlights the practical feasibility of the hybrid FFT–MUSIC methodology for real-world TWRI scenarios. With the advent of resource-rich modern hardware platforms, the computational burden of the proposed FFT-MUSIC framework can be significantly mitigated, enabling practical real-time high-resolution TWRI imaging.

Keywords: Through-the-wall, high-resolution, image reconstruction, subspace, computational complexity

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1 Introduction

Through-the-wall radar imaging (TWRI) has emerged as an important sensing technology in modern electronic warfare, civil protection and military tactical operations, for observing non-contact human activity and concealed structural features [1]-[3]. It facilitates situational awareness in environments where direct observation is impossible [4]-[6]. High-resolution imaging radar can capture detailed electronic signatures and emissions from enemy systems, providing valuable intelligence on enemy capabilities, tactics, and movements [7]-[9].

TWRI has become increasingly significant in modern electronic warfare due to its ability to provide actionable intelligence in denied or obstructed environments [10]-[12]. It enables forces to detect, localize, and track targets behind walls and urban structures without direct line of sight, which is critical in dense urban battlefields. This capability enhances operational safety by reducing the need for blind entry into potentially hostile areas and supports tactical decision making with real-time situational awareness. TWRI also contributes to surveillance and reconnaissance missions by enabling continuous monitoring of enclosed spaces while maintaining a safe stand-off distance. From a technological perspective, it drives the development of advanced signal processing techniques that can operate under severe clutter, multipath propagation, and low signal-to-noise conditions commonly encountered in urban warfare [13]-[15].

Frequency-modulated continuous wave (FMCW) radar offers a highly effective solution for through-the-wall applications [16]. It facilitates accurate target localization and high-resolution range measurements using wideband chirp signals [17]. Its continuous transmission enhances sensitivity to weak target echoes that are heavily attenuated by wall materials, thereby improving detection reliability. The choice of operating frequency is a fundamental design consideration in through-the-wall imaging, driven by the trade-off between penetration capability and spatial resolution. The 1 – 3 GHz band is widely regarded as the most suitable range, as it enables sufficient penetration through common building materials while preserving meaningful imaging detail [18]. At these frequencies, electromagnetic waves experience reduced attenuation compared to higher bands, allowing reliable detection of concealed targets. However, lower frequencies inherently limit spatial resolution for TWRI. This limitation can be effectively addressed through the use of multiple antennas and array processing techniques, which enhance angular resolution and imaging performance [19]. This balance makes the 1 – 3 GHz range particularly well suited for practical TWRI systems operating in complex and obstructed environments..

Extensive research contributions have been documented in literature regarding high-resolution through-the-wall radar imaging, for estimation of target signatures such as range, velocity, and direction of arrival (DOA) [20]-[23]. The authors in [24] presented a comprehensive survey on through-the-wall imaging, to characterize the effects of attenuation and strong wall reflections. The authors in [25] presented numerical evaluation of conventional beamforming (CBF) and range migration algorithm (RMA), for image reconstruction in the context of

TWRI. Subspace methods offer high resolution and robust direction finding, particularly in the presence of noise and closely-spaced sources [26]. MUSIC and its variants exploit the eigen decomposition of the covariance matrix of received signals, to estimate the DOA with substantial accuracy [27]. However, these DF methods suffer from the limitation of rigorous computational complexity. The authors in [28] proposed a robust scheme for target range and velocity estimation, based on Fourier transform (FT) and multiple signal classification (MUSIC). In [29], the authors presented a robust high-resolution method for FMCW radar parameters estimation, based on modified MUSIC with reduced computations. The authors in [30] proposed a novel image reconstruction methodology, using S-band multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) radar and a convolutional neural network (CNN).

This paper presents high-resolution hybrid imaging methodology for FMCW based through-the-wall MIMO radar systems. It provides quantitative insight into the tradeoffs between high-resolution image reconstruction and computational burden, to validate the feasibility of the proposed approach. A robust imaging chain is formulated based on FT and subspace-based hybrid image reconstruction (HIR) approach for TWRI scenario. Moreover, a comprehensive analytical model is formulated for the proposed imaging scheme alongwith FT based algorithm, Omega-K based RMA, and CBF approach. Extensive simulations and comparisons are conducted under various multi-target scenarios to evaluate the performance of each method. Furthermore, comprehensive computational complexity analysis are performed, to validate the robustness of the proposed approach in practical TWRI scenarios.

In this work, the MUSIC algorithm is implemented in two different configurations to analyze the tradeoff between computational efficiency and exhaustive angular estimation. In the first configuration, MUSIC is applied after CFAR detection on the range-Doppler map. Consequently, angle estimation is performed only for detected targets, which significantly reduces computational complexity. In the second configuration, MUSIC is directly applied after the range FFT stage on all range bins without prior target detection. Although this approach enables complete angular analysis across the entire radar scene, it introduces substantially higher computational burden due to repeated covariance estimation, eigen-decomposition, and angular spectrum evaluation for every range bin. Therefore, the CFAR-assisted MUSIC framework provides a more computationally efficient solution for real-time TWRI systems.

The research paper is segregated into different sections. Section II provides a comprehensive overview of the different challenges associated with TWRI. Section III demonstrates overall system model blocks, with comprehensive analytical problem formulation. Section IV presents different image reconstruction (IR) algorithms including existing and proposed hybrid FFT-subspace based imaging methodology. Section V provides comprehensive computational complexity analysis of the proposed imaging approach, alongwith comparative evaluation of existing imaging approaches. Section VI presents numerical simulation results,

comparisons and thorough analysis to validate the proposed approach. Finally, section VII summarizes the research paper with concluding remarks.

2 Challenges of TWRI

2.1 Signal Attenuation and Distortion

Through-the-wall radar imaging faces a set of fundamental challenges that arise from the complex interaction between electromagnetic waves and obstructing structures [31]-[33]. A primary difficulty is the strong attenuation and distortion introduced by wall materials. Common building media such as concrete, brick, and reinforced composites exhibit frequency-dependent permittivity and conductivity. These properties lead to significant signal loss, phase distortion, and reduced penetration depth [34]. As a result, the back-scattered signals from targets behind the wall are often weak and highly corrupted, which directly limits detection sensitivity and image fidelity. The variability of wall composition further complicates the problem, since accurate prior knowledge of material parameters is rarely available in practical deployments [35]. Let us model the wall as a homogeneous flat slab of thickness d with complex permittivity ε_c , given by:

$$\varepsilon_c = \varepsilon' - j\varepsilon'' \quad (1)$$

Equivalently, the imaginary part can be expressed in terms of conductivity σ as:

$$\varepsilon_c = \varepsilon' - j\frac{\sigma}{\omega} \quad (2)$$

where $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency. We assume the wall is non-magnetic so $\mu = \mu_0$. The radar transmits a plane wave which is incident on the wall at or near normal incidence. Inside a lossy dielectric the complex propagation constant γ is:

$$\gamma = \alpha + j\beta = j\omega\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon_c} \quad (3)$$

For $\varepsilon_c = \varepsilon_0\varepsilon_r - j\frac{\sigma}{\omega}$, the attenuation constant α and phase constant β can be expressed in terms of $\varepsilon' = \varepsilon_0\varepsilon_r$ and σ as [33]:

$$\alpha = \omega\sqrt{\frac{\mu\varepsilon'}{2}} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\omega\varepsilon'}\right)^2} - 1 \right]^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = \omega\sqrt{\frac{\mu\varepsilon'}{2}} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\omega\varepsilon'}\right)^2} + 1 \right]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

These are derived by evaluating $j\omega\sqrt{\mu(\varepsilon' - j\sigma/\omega)}$ and separating real and imaginary parts. This formulation is standard for lossy-media plane propagation.

If $\sigma/(\omega\epsilon') \ll 1$, then the material is weakly lossy and α is small. If $\sigma/(\omega\epsilon') \gg 1$, then the attenuation grows and propagation inside the slab is strongly damped.

When an electromagnetic wave radiated by the FMCW through-the-wall radar encounters a dielectric wall, an impedance discontinuity arises between free space and the wall material. This discontinuity causes the incident electromagnetic field to split into two components: a reflected component returning toward the radar and a transmitted component propagating inside the wall medium. Consider free space with intrinsic impedance $\eta_1 \approx 377 \Omega$ and a wall characterized by complex permittivity ϵ_c . The intrinsic impedance of the wall medium can be represented as [34]:

$$\eta_2 = \sqrt{\frac{j\omega\mu_0}{\sigma + j\omega\epsilon_0\epsilon_r}} \quad (6)$$

At the air-to-wall interface, the tangential electric and magnetic fields must satisfy electromagnetic boundary conditions. Consequently, the Fresnel reflection coefficient can be expressed as:

$$\Gamma_{aw} = \frac{\eta_2 - \eta_1}{\eta_2 + \eta_1} \quad (7)$$

which represents the ratio of reflected electric field amplitude to incident electric field amplitude. This reflected component is responsible for the dominant front-wall clutter observed in through-the-wall radar imaging systems. Simultaneously, part of the incident wave penetrates the wall, and the associated air-to-wall transmission coefficient is given by:

$$T_{aw} = \frac{2\eta_2}{\eta_2 + \eta_1} \quad (8)$$

Thus, the transmitted electric field inside the wall can be expressed as:

$$E_t = T_{aw}E_i \quad (9)$$

where E_i denotes the incident electric field. When the electromagnetic wave propagating in air encounters the dielectric wall at an oblique angle, its propagation direction changes due to the difference in propagation velocities between air and wall medium. This bending phenomenon is known as refraction and is governed by Snell's law [35]:

$$n_1 \sin \theta_i = n_2 \sin \theta_t \quad (10)$$

where θ_i and θ_t denote the angles of incidence and refraction, respectively, while n_1 and n_2 are the refractive indices of air and wall medium. Since the wall permittivity is higher than that of air, the propagation velocity inside the wall decreases to:

$$v_w = \frac{c}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (11)$$

This change in propagation velocity causes the transmitted wave to bend toward the surface normal. Consequently, the electromagnetic path inside the wall differs from the free-space propagation path, introducing propagation delay, phase distortion, and target localization errors in through-the-wall radar imaging systems. . When the wave reaches the second boundary between the wall and free space, another impedance mismatch occurs. The wall-to-air reflection coefficient is

$$\Gamma_{wa} = \frac{\eta_1 - \eta_2}{\eta_1 + \eta_2} \quad (12)$$

while the wall-to-air transmission coefficient is:

$$T_{wa} = \frac{2\eta_1}{\eta_1 + \eta_2} \quad (13)$$

This coefficient governs the fraction of the electromagnetic field transmitted from the wall into the indoor environment containing the target. Consequently, the overall transmission through the wall is determined by the combined effect of the air-to-wall transmission, propagation through the lossy wall, and wall-to-air transmission. The total wall transmission coefficient is therefore expressed as:

$$T_{\text{wall}} = T_{aw}T_{wa}e^{-\gamma d_w} \quad (14)$$

or equivalently,

$$T_{\text{wall}} = T_{aw}T_{wa}e^{-\alpha d_w} e^{-j\beta d_w} \quad (15)$$

In practical through-the-wall radar scenarios, the radar signal traverses the wall twice, once during forward propagation toward the target and again during the return propagation toward the radar receiver. Hence, the overall two-way wall transmission effect becomes:

$$T_{\text{two-way}} = (T_{aw}T_{wa}e^{-\Gamma d_w})^2 \quad (16)$$

This two-way transmission factor directly governs the attenuation and phase distortion imposed on the target echo. Higher wall permittivity, conductivity, and thickness increase reflection losses and attenuation, thereby reducing penetration capability and degrading target detectability in FMCW through-the-wall radar imaging systems.

2.2 Wall Penetration and Resolution Trade-off

A fundamental design trade-off in through-the-wall radar imaging exists between penetration capability and spatial resolution, and it strongly influences the choice of operating frequency [36]. Lower frequencies, typically in the range of 1–3 GHz, are preferred because they experience less attenuation when propagating through lossy building materials such as concrete and brick. This improved penetration arises from reduced dielectric loss and weaker scattering,

which allows the electromagnetic waves to reach targets behind walls with sufficient energy for detection. However, operating at lower frequencies inherently limits achievable resolution [37]. Range resolution is directly proportional to signal bandwidth, which is often constrained at lower frequencies, while cross-range resolution depends on wavelength, with longer wavelengths leading to poorer spatial discrimination. As a result, fine structural details and closely spaced targets become more difficult to resolve. Conversely, higher frequencies offer superior resolution due to shorter wavelengths and wider available bandwidth, but they suffer from severe attenuation and reduced penetration depth in typical wall materials [38]. This trade-off necessitates a careful balance in system design, where the selected frequency band must ensure adequate penetration while maintaining acceptable resolution for the intended application. Consequently, the 1 – 3 GHz band represents a practical compromise that enables reliable sensing through common structures, while preserving sufficient imaging capability for detection and localization tasks.

2.3 Wall Clutter and Multipath

Another critical challenge lies in the presence of severe clutter generated by the wall itself and by objects within the environment [39]. The front wall produces dominant reflections that can mask weaker target returns. Internal structures such as furniture, wiring, and structural reinforcements create additional multipath components that overlap in time and space with the desired signals. This leads to ambiguity in range and angle estimation and increases the likelihood of false alarms. The clutter environment is often non-stationary, which makes adaptive suppression difficult and demands robust statistical modeling [40].

Multipath propagation is a persistent and complex issue in through-the-wall scenarios. Signals can undergo multiple reflections between walls, floors, and objects before reaching the receiver [41]. These indirect paths introduce ghost targets and spatial smearing in reconstructed images. The resulting artifacts degrade imaging resolution and reduce localization accuracy. The problem is further exacerbated in confined environments where reverberation effects are strong, and where the geometry is not well defined.

2.4 Robust Signal Processing for TWRI

From a signal processing perspective, the need for robust and computationally efficient algorithms is a significant concern. Advanced imaging methods such as sparse reconstruction and compressive sensing can improve performance in challenging environments, but they often require high computational resources and careful parameter tuning [42]. Real-time operation is difficult to achieve when processing large datasets with complex inversion techniques. This creates a trade-off between image quality and computational feasibility, which is critical for operational systems.

Motion of targets and the platform introduces additional complexity. Human targets behind walls may exhibit micro-motions such as breathing or slight

movements, which can be exploited for detection but also complicate coherent integration. Platform motion can lead to phase errors and image defocusing if not properly compensated. Synchronization and stability of the radar system are therefore essential to maintain coherent processing gains [43].

Finally, practical deployment constraints pose nontrivial challenges. Antenna placement, limited access to the scene, and regulatory restrictions on transmit power and frequency bands all influence system performance [44]. Environmental factors such as moisture, temperature, and structural variability further affect propagation characteristics. These constraints require careful system design and adaptive operation to ensure reliable performance across diverse scenarios. Collectively, these challenges define the research landscape of through-the-wall radar imaging and motivate ongoing advancements in modeling, hardware design, and signal processing methodologies [45].

3 System Model

3.1 Signal Model

The transmitted signal of an FMCW radar is a linear frequency-modulated (chirp) signal, which can be expressed as:

$$s_T(t) = Ae^{j2\pi(f_o t + \frac{1}{2}\mu t^2)} \quad (17)$$

where A is the amplitude of transmitted signal, f_o is the carrier frequency, and $\mu = \frac{B}{T}$ is the chirp rate.

$$s_T(t) = e^{j2\pi f_T t} \quad (18)$$

where $f_T = f_o + \frac{1}{2}\mu t$ represents the frequency, which increases linearly with time. The received signal is a time-delayed and Doppler-shifted version of the transmitted signal, expressed as:

$$s_R(t) = Ae^{j2\pi(f_o(t-\tau) + \frac{1}{2}\mu(t-\tau)^2 + f_D t)} \quad (19)$$

where τ is the time delay, and f_D is the Doppler frequency shift given by:

$$\tau = \frac{2R}{c} \quad (20)$$

$$f_D = \frac{2v f_o}{c} \quad (21)$$

where R and v represent the range and velocity of the target. The beat frequency f_b is obtained by mixing the transmitted and received signals.

3.2 Virtual Array Formation

Consider a linear transmit array of N_t isotropic elements with element position vector d_t and a receive array of N_r isotropic elements with element position vector d_r . The array patterns of the transmit and receive arrays, in Fig. 1 (a), can be represented as:

$$A_t(\phi) = \sum_{n=1}^{N_t} \psi_{t,n} e^{-jk d_{t,n}(\sin\phi - \sin\phi_s)} \quad (22)$$

$$A_r(\phi) = \sum_{n=1}^{N_r} \psi_{r,n} e^{-jk d_{r,n}(\sin\phi - \sin\phi_s)} \quad (23)$$

where $k = 2\pi/\lambda_0$, λ_0 is the free-space wavelength, $w_{t,n}$ and $w_{r,n}$ are the real-valued amplitude weights of the n^{th} array element in the transmit and receive array, respectively, and ϕ_s is the scan angle. According to the concept of MIMO radar arrays, if the transmitted signals from each transmit antenna are orthogonal, then each receive antenna receives N_t different reflected signals from a target. This results in the concept of the virtual array, as shown in Fig. 1. It encompasses number of elements N_v , whose element positions are all the possible combinations of the transmit and receive antenna positions. The number of virtual array elements, in Fig. 1 (b), can be expressed as:

$$N_v = N_t N_r \quad (24)$$

Theorem 1 (Rehan's Subspace Theorem). Assume $x_v(t)$ represents the virtual array observation vector:

$$\mathbf{x}_v(t) = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{s}(t) + \mathbf{n}(t) \quad (25)$$

where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_v \times P}$ is the steering matrix, $\mathbf{s}(t)$ is the source signal vector, and $\mathbf{n}(t)$ is the additive white Gaussian noise. Then, the covariance matrix

$$\mathbf{R}_v = E\{\mathbf{x}_v(t)\mathbf{x}_v^H(t)\} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{R}_s \mathbf{A}^H + \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I} \quad (26)$$

preserves the signal subspace i.e.,

$$\text{span}(\mathbf{U}_s^v) = \text{span}(\mathbf{A}) \quad (27)$$

where \mathbf{U}_s^v represents the eigen-subspace of \mathbf{R}_v associated with the P dominant eigenvalues.

Proof. Starting from the definition of covariance matrix,

$$\mathbf{R}_v = \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{x}_v(t)\mathbf{x}_v^H(t)\} \quad (28)$$

substituting $\mathbf{x}_v(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{s}(t) + \mathbf{n}(t)$ yields

$$\mathbf{R}_v = \mathbb{E}\{(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s}(t) + \mathbf{n}(t))(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s}(t) + \mathbf{n}(t))^H\} \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s}(t)\mathbf{s}^H(t)\mathbf{A}^H + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{s}(t)\mathbf{n}^H(t) \\ &\quad + \mathbf{n}(t)\mathbf{s}^H(t)\mathbf{A}^H + \mathbf{n}(t)\mathbf{n}^H(t)\} \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Using linearity of expectation, this becomes:

$$\mathbf{R}_v = \mathbf{A}\mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{s}(t)\mathbf{s}^H(t)\}\mathbf{A}^H + \mathbf{A}\mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{s}(t)\mathbf{n}^H(t)\} \quad (31)$$

$$+ \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{n}(t)\mathbf{s}^H(t)\}\mathbf{A}^H + \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{n}(t)\mathbf{n}^H(t)\} \quad (32)$$

Assuming that the signal and noise are uncorrelated, we have:

$$\mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{s}(t)\mathbf{n}^H(t)\} = \mathbf{0} \quad (33)$$

and since the noise is white Gaussian,

$$\mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{n}(t)\mathbf{n}^H(t)\} = \sigma_n^2\mathbf{I} \quad (34)$$

Let $\mathbf{R}_s = \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{s}(t)\mathbf{s}^H(t)\}$ Then,

$$\mathbf{R}_v = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{R}_s\mathbf{A}^H + \sigma_n^2\mathbf{I} \quad (35)$$

Next, define:

$$\mathbf{R}_x = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{R}_s\mathbf{A}^H \quad (36)$$

Thus,

$$\mathbf{R}_v = \mathbf{R}_x + \sigma_n^2\mathbf{I} \quad (37)$$

Let $(\lambda_i, \mathbf{u}_i)$ be an eigenpair of \mathbf{R}_x , i.e.,

$$\mathbf{R}_x\mathbf{u}_i = \lambda_i\mathbf{u}_i \quad (38)$$

Then,

$$\mathbf{R}_v\mathbf{u}_i = (\mathbf{R}_x + \sigma_n^2\mathbf{I})\mathbf{u}_i \quad (39)$$

$$= \mathbf{R}_x\mathbf{u}_i + \sigma_n^2\mathbf{u}_i \quad (40)$$

$$= (\lambda_i + \sigma_n^2)\mathbf{u}_i \quad (41)$$

Thus, the eigenvectors of \mathbf{R}_v are identical to those of \mathbf{R}_x , and the eigenvalues are shifted by σ_n^2 .

Since $\mathbf{R}_x = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{R}_s\mathbf{A}^H$ has rank P , it follows that \mathbf{R}_v has P dominant eigenvalues corresponding to the signal subspace. Moreover, the column space of \mathbf{R}_x is equal to the column space of \mathbf{A} , i.e.,

$$\text{span}(\mathbf{R}_x) = \text{span}(\mathbf{A}). \quad (42)$$

Therefore, the eigenvectors corresponding to the P largest eigenvalues of \mathbf{R}_v span the same subspace as \mathbf{A} :

$$\text{span}(\mathbf{U}_v^s) = \text{span}(\mathbf{A}) \quad (43)$$

This completes the proof.

Lemma 1. Let $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times P}$ with $\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}) = P$, and let $\mathbf{R}_s \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times P}$ be a positive definite matrix (i.e., $\text{rank}(\mathbf{R}_s) = P$). Then,

$$\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{R}_s\mathbf{A}^H) = P \quad (44)$$

Proof. Using the rank inequality,

$$\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{R}_s\mathbf{A}^H) \leq \min\{\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}), \text{rank}(\mathbf{R}_s), \text{rank}(\mathbf{A}^H)\} \quad (45)$$

Since

$$\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}) = \text{rank}(\mathbf{A}^H) = P, \quad \text{rank}(\mathbf{R}_s) = P \quad (46)$$

We obtain

$$\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{R}_s\mathbf{A}^H) \leq P \quad (47)$$

Fig. 1: (a) Antenna configuration (b) Virtual array formation

3.3 Overall System Model

Fig. 2 outlines the step-wise description of the proposed system for TWRI. The received radar echoes from multiple antenna elements are sampled to produce digital data for further processing. This digitized data is then fed into the channel splicing block, which forms a virtual antenna array by combining information from multiple physical channels. Afterwards, the wall clutter removal block is incorporated for mitigating strong, static reflections caused by the wall itself, which can otherwise mask or obscure the presence of behind-the-wall targets. Techniques such as background subtraction or subspace filtering are often employed to isolate target reflections from dominant wall echoes.

Fig. 2: Imaging chain for TWR

Subsequently, FFT is performed along the fast-time (range) dimension, converting time-domain signals into range profiles and enabling precise range estimation of targets. These range profiles are then passed to the image reconstruction (IR) block, which applies advanced imaging algorithms such as conventional beamforming (CBF), range migration algorithm (RMA), Fourier-based and subspace-based methods to estimate the azimuth angle of targets. Additionally, a dotted path in the block diagram represents an optional processing branch for velocity estimation. In this path, a second FFT is applied along the slow-time dimension, to generate a range-Doppler map that provides both range and velocity information.

4 Imaging Algorithms for TWRI

In order to understand the concept of imaging in TWRI, it is important to realize that radar does not see things as we humans do. The radar image is actually a top-down view, and represents the image as down-range away from the radar versus cross-range across the radar. Radar imaging is observed in the form of dots or blobs [15, 16]. When there is one target behind the wall, a single blob is observed. Similarly, two blobs are observed for the case of two targets, and so forth.

4.1 Conventional Beamforming (CBF)

CBF is a fundamental technique used for angle estimation in radar imaging systems equipped with antenna arrays [11]. In CBF, the signals received at each antenna element are shifted to align the contributions from a specific direction, and then summed together. The direction that yields the maximum output power indicates the estimated angle of arrival.

4.2 RMA based IR

The RMA is employed to correct for the migration of target echoes across range cells, for accurate focusing and imaging of the target [17]. Range compression is achieved by performing a matched filter operation on the received signal. Range migration correction involves transforming the range-compressed data to correct for the migration of target echoes across range cells. Azimuth compression is achieved by performing matched filtering in the azimuth domain.

4.3 FT Based IR

FFT is very useful approach for accurate angle estimation, because of its computational efficiency and simple implementation. By performing an FFT across the spatial dimension i.e., across the antenna elements, the radar effectively transforms the received signals into the angular domain. However, its resolution is not sufficient to separate closely located targets. Moreover, it suffers from leakage and sidelobes, which can obscure weaker targets near strong ones.

4.4 Proposed Subspace Based HIR

Multiple signal classification (MUSIC) is a high-resolution direction-finding algorithm based on eigen-structure of the received signal. Element-space (ES) MUSIC belongs to the family of subspace based algorithms, that utilizes the original spatial domain of the antenna array elements, rather than transforming the data into beamspace or other domains. Fig. 3 shows the flow chart of the hybrid FT-ES-MUSIC-IR algorithm for parameter estimation of multiple targets.

Firstly, the covariance matrix of the received signal is computed. Then, the eigen-decomposition of this covariance matrix is performed to evaluate matrices of eigen-values and eigen-vectors. The eigen-values are arranged in the descending order to segregate the signal and noise subspaces. When an arrival vector is orthogonal to the noise subspace, the peaks of pseudospectrum correspond to the desired directions of arrival.

The proposed methodology offers three modes of operation for visualization of reconstructed images. The mode selection criteria M_{sel} can be represented as:

$$M_{sel} = \begin{cases} M_{RD} & ; \psi \in Mode - I \\ M_{RA} & ; \psi \in Mode - II \\ M_{RD} + M_{RA} & ; \psi \in Mode - III \end{cases} \quad (48)$$

where M_{sel} is a control variable to configure the radar display, based on the graphical user interface (GUI) mode selection parameter ψ . In this work, Mode-I is configured to visualize the range-Doppler map (RDM) i.e., M_{RD} to display target range versus velocity. The Mode-I operation is used for target detection in cluttered environments, speed estimation of moving targets, and micro-Doppler analysis.

Fig. 3: Flowchart of proposed methodology

Moreover, Mode-II is selected to visualize the range-angle map (RAM) i.e., M_{RA} to display target range versus azimuth angle. The Mode-II operation is used for localization of targets in range and angle, indoor human activity monitoring, MIMO radar imaging and beamforming systems. Furthermore, Mode-III is envisaged to visualize both the RDM and RAM representation. The Mode-III operation is used for multi-target tracking in autonomous driving, drone detection and classification, surveillance systems for full 3D situational awareness.

In this work, the MUSIC algorithm is implemented in two different configurations to analyze the tradeoff between computational efficiency and exhaustive angular estimation. In the first configuration, MUSIC is applied after OS-CFAR detection on the range-Doppler map. Consequently, angle estimation is performed only for detected targets, which significantly reduces computational complexity. In the second configuration, MUSIC is directly applied after the

range FFT stage on all range bins without prior target detection. Although this approach enables complete angular analysis across the entire radar scene, it introduces substantially higher computational burden due to repeated covariance estimation, eigen-decomposition, and angular spectrum evaluation for every range bin. Therefore, the OS-CFAR-assisted MUSIC framework provides a more computationally efficient solution for real-time TWRI systems.

5 Computational Complexity Analysis

5.1 Computational Cost of Proposed Methodology

This section presents the cost of each stage in the hybrid image reconstruction process for through-the-wall radar imaging, highlighting how the algorithm scales with data dimensions. The received radar echoes are organized into a three-dimensional radar data cube consisting of fast-time samples, slow-time sweeps, and antenna channels. Let N_s , N_p , and N_a denote the number of fast-time samples, slow-time sweeps, and antenna elements, respectively. The total number of acquired radar samples is therefore given by $N_s N_p N_a$. Since data acquisition and cube formation primarily involve sampling, indexing, and memory storage operations, the computational complexity grows linearly with the total number of samples. Hence, the complexity of radar data cube formation is expressed as:

$$C_{cube} = \mathcal{O}(N_s N_p N_a) \quad (49)$$

For the considered TWRI framework with $N_s = 1024$, $N_p = 128$, and $N_a = 8$, the total number of processed samples becomes approximately 1.05×10^6 . Therefore, the data acquisition stage introduces relatively moderate computational overhead compared with the subsequent signal processing stages. After cube formation, channel splicing is performed to concatenate data from all antenna channels into a unified observation matrix for further processing. This operation mainly consists of memory reorganization and concatenation of antenna snapshots. Since each radar sample is accessed once during the splicing operation, the computational complexity also scales linearly with the total number of acquired samples. Therefore, the complexity of channel splicing is given by:

$$C_{splice} = \mathcal{O}(N_s N_p N_a) \quad (50)$$

Following channel splicing, wall clutter suppression is performed using the iterative empirical mode decomposition (EMD) algorithm. The EMD algorithm iteratively decomposes the received radar signal into multiple intrinsic mode functions (IMFs) through repeated extrema detection, spline interpolation, envelope estimation, and sifting operations. According to the literature, the computational complexity of EMD approximately follows FFT-order behavior and may be represented as:

$$C_{EMD}(N) = \mathcal{O}(KIN \log N) \quad (51)$$

where K denotes the number of extracted IMFs, I denotes the number of sifting iterations per IMF, and N represents the signal length. This result demonstrates that iterative EMD clutter suppression constitutes the dominant computational stage in the overall TWRI processing chain due to repeated iterative decomposition and interpolation operations. After clutter suppression, range estimation is performed by applying FFT along the fast-time dimension. For each antenna channel and slow-time sweep, an N_s -point FFT is computed. Since the computational complexity of FFT is $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$, the total range FFT complexity is expressed as:

$$C_{range} = \mathcal{O}(N_a N_p N_s \log N_s) \quad (52)$$

Subsequently, Doppler FFT is performed along the slow-time dimension to estimate target velocity. For each range bin and antenna channel, an N_p -point FFT is computed. The corresponding computational complexity is therefore expressed as:

$$C_{doppler} = \mathcal{O}(N_a N_s N_p \log N_p) \quad (53)$$

The combined range FFT and Doppler FFT stages form the two-dimensional range-Doppler processing framework used for joint range and velocity estimation. Following range-Doppler processing, ordered statistics CFAR (OS-CFAR) detection is applied to identify target cells in the two-dimensional range-Doppler map. Let W denote the CFAR window size. For every cell under test, the algorithm extracts neighboring reference cells, sorts the samples, estimates the adaptive threshold, and compares the threshold with the CUT power level. Since the dominant operation is sorting, the computational complexity for each CUT becomes $\mathcal{O}(W \log W)$. Considering all range-Doppler cells, the total OS-CFAR computational complexity is expressed as:

$$C_{CFAR} = \mathcal{O}(N_s N_p W \log W) \quad (54)$$

Hence, OS-CFAR contributes substantial computational overhead because threshold estimation and sorting operations are performed for every range-Doppler cell. After target detection, high-resolution angle estimation is performed using the MUSIC algorithm. The MUSIC processing chain consists of covariance matrix estimation, eigenvalue decomposition, noise subspace formation, and angular spectrum scanning. The covariance matrix estimation stage computes:

$$\mathbf{R}_{xx} = \frac{1}{L} \mathbf{X} \mathbf{X}^H \quad (55)$$

where L represents the number of snapshots. The complexity of covariance estimation is therefore:

$$C_{cov} = \mathcal{O}(N_a^2 L) \quad (56)$$

Next, eigenvalue decomposition is performed on the $N_a \times N_a$ covariance matrix to separate signal and noise subspaces. The computational complexity of eigenvalue decomposition is given by:

$$C_{EVD} = \mathcal{O}(N_a^3) \quad (57)$$

Finally, MUSIC angular spectrum scanning is performed across N_θ candidate angular grid points. For each angle, the pseudospectrum evaluation requires matrix-vector multiplications involving the noise subspace. The corresponding computational complexity is expressed as:

$$C_{scan} = \mathcal{O}(N_\theta N_a^2) \quad (58)$$

Table 1 presents the stepwise computational cost of each stage in the hybrid image reconstruction process for through-the-wall radar imaging. Assuming $N_\theta = 180$ angular grid points, the complexity for single-iteration of MUSIC algorithm can be expressed as:

$$C_{MUSIC} = \mathcal{O}(N_a^2 L + N_a^3 + N_\theta N_a^2) \quad (59)$$

In this work, the MUSIC algorithm is employed in two different processing configurations to investigate the tradeoff between computational efficiency and exhaustive angular estimation capability. In the first configuration, MUSIC is applied after the formation of the range-Doppler map and subsequent OS-CFAR target detection stage. In this case, angle estimation is performed only for the detected target cells. Therefore, the number of MUSIC executions is equal to the number of detected targets, which significantly reduces the overall computational burden. This approach avoids unnecessary angular spectrum evaluation in noise or clutter-dominated regions, and enables computationally efficient high-resolution DOA estimation. Consequently, the overall computational cost can be expressed as:

$$C_{MUSIC-I} = \mathcal{O}(N_t(N_a^2 L + N_a^3 + N_\theta N_a^2)) \quad (60)$$

Substituting the considered system parameters, $N_a = 8$, $L = 128$, $N_\theta = 180$, the complexity of a single MUSIC execution becomes approximately $\mathcal{O}(2.02 \times 10^4)$. Now, if five targets are detected after OS-CFAR, the total complexity becomes approximately $\mathcal{O}(1.01 \times 10^5)$. This computational load remains relatively small because MUSIC processing is performed only on a limited number of detected target cells.

In the second approach, MUSIC is directly applied after range FFT processing without prior OS-CFAR detection. In this configuration, angle estimation is independently performed for every range bin. Since the total number of range bins equals N_s , MUSIC must be executed N_s times. Consequently, the overall computational complexity becomes:

$$C_{MUSIC-II} = \mathcal{O}(N_s(N_a^2 L + N_a^3 + N_\theta N_a^2)) \quad (61)$$

Substituting the system parameters, $N_s = 1024$ yields approximately $\mathcal{O}(2.07 \times 10^7)$. Therefore, applying MUSIC on every range bin introduces significantly

larger computational burden compared with applying MUSIC only after OS-CFAR target detection. The computational reduction achieved through CFAR-assisted MUSIC processing can be quantified by the ratio:

$$\frac{C_{MUSIC-II}}{C_{MUSIC-I}} = \frac{N_s}{N_t} \quad (62)$$

This expression shows that the complexity reduction directly depends on the ratio between total range bins and detected targets. For example, if ten targets are present, then first approach outperforms the second one by a factor of approximately 100. From a practical TWRI perspective, the first approach is computationally efficient because high-resolution angle estimation is performed only on detected target locations. This significantly reduces covariance estimation, eigen-decomposition, and angular scanning operations. In contrast, direct MUSIC processing across all range bins performs unnecessary angle estimation in empty or clutter-dominated bins, thereby introducing substantial redundant computations. Overall, the computational complexity of the proposed high-resolution TWRI methodology is dominated by the iterative EMD clutter suppression stage and subspace-based MUSIC framework.

Table 1: Computational complexity for proposed TWRI pipeline

Stage	Computational Cost
Data acquisition	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a)$
Channel splicing	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a)$
Wall clutter removal	$\Theta(K N_s N_p N_a)$
Range FFT	$\Theta(N_a N_p N_s \log N_s)$
Doppler FFT	$\Theta(N_a N_s N_p \log N_p)$
OS-CFAR	$\Theta(N_s N_p W \log W)$
MUSIC (one run)	$\Theta(M^2 L + M^3 + GM^2)$

Proposition 1. *Assume processing pipeline: Range FFT \rightarrow Doppler FFT \rightarrow CFAR \rightarrow MUSIC (per target detection). Assume T be the number of target detections, C_R be the cost of range FFT, C_D be the cost of Doppler FFT, C_{CFAR} be the cost of target detection, and C_M be the cost of single MUSIC run, the total computational cost is:*

$$C = C_R + C_D + C_{CFAR} + TC_M \quad (63)$$

In this processing flow, the received radar data first undergoes a Range FFT along the fast-time dimension to estimate target ranges. Next, a Doppler FFT is applied along the slow-time dimension to obtain the range–Doppler map, which

represents both range and relative motion of scatterers. The CFAR detector is then applied to this map to identify potential target bins while suppressing noise and clutter. Finally, the MUSIC algorithm is executed only on the CFAR-detected target bins to estimate their directions of arrival (DOA) and form the high-resolution range-angle map (RAM). This pipeline minimizes the number of MUSIC runs because the algorithm is executed only for detected targets, making it computationally efficient for sparse target scenes.

Proposition 2. *Assume processing pipeline: Range FFT \rightarrow MUSIC on every range bin. Assume N_s be the number of fast-time samples, C_R be the cost of range FFT, and C_M be the cost of single MUSIC run, the total computational cost is:*

$$C = C_R + N_s C_M \quad (64)$$

In this approach, the received radar data is first processed using the Range FFT to extract range information. Instead of performing Doppler FFT and CFAR detection, the MUSIC algorithm is directly applied to each range bin across all range cells. This means MUSIC runs are executed N_s times, where N_s is the total number of range bins. Each run estimates the angular spectrum for its corresponding range bin, producing a direct range-angle map without requiring Doppler information. While this approach simplifies the processing chain and improves robustness in dense or ambiguous Doppler environments, it significantly increases computational cost because MUSIC is performed for every range cell rather than only for detected targets.

5.2 Computational Cost of 3D-FFT Based Imaging

The 3D-FFT imaging framework begins with radar data acquisition and formation of the three-dimensional radar data cube. The received radar echoes are sampled across fast-time, slow-time, and spatial antenna dimensions, to formulate the radar cube. Table 2 demonstrates the stepwise computational cost of TWRI using 3D-FFT approach. After data cube formation, channel splicing is performed to concatenate the received signals from all antenna channels into a unified spatial observation matrix. This operation primarily involves memory rearrangement and indexing operations. Subsequently, wall clutter suppression is performed using iterative empirical mode decomposition (EMD). The EMD algorithm iteratively decomposes the received radar signal into multiple intrinsic mode functions through repeated extrema detection, spline interpolation, mean envelope estimation, and sifting operations.

After clutter removal, range estimation is performed using FFT along the fast-time dimension. For every antenna channel and slow-time sweep, an N_s -point FFT is computed. Since FFT complexity scales as $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$, the range FFT complexity becomes:

$$C_{range} = \mathcal{O}(N_a N_p N_s \log N_s) \quad (65)$$

The range FFT stage extracts target range information and forms the first dimension of the three-dimensional imaging framework. Following range processing, Doppler FFT is applied along the slow-time dimension to estimate target velocity. For every range bin and antenna channel, an N_p -point FFT is computed. Therefore, the Doppler FFT complexity is expressed as:

$$C_{doppler} = \mathcal{O}(N_a N_s N_p \log N_p) \quad (66)$$

The range FFT and Doppler FFT stages jointly form the two-dimensional range-Doppler map for target range and velocity estimation. Instead of applying the MUSIC algorithm for angle estimation, the proposed framework employs spatial FFT across the antenna array dimension to extract target angular information. This operation completes the three-dimensional FFT imaging chain for simultaneous estimation of target range, velocity, and angle. For every range-Doppler cell, an N_a -point FFT is computed across the spatial antenna dimension. Therefore, the angular FFT computational complexity becomes:

$$C_{angle} = \mathcal{O}(N_s N_p N_a \log N_a) \quad (67)$$

Hence, the angular FFT stage introduces substantially lower computational burden than subspace-based MUSIC processing because FFT avoids covariance estimation, eigen-decomposition, and angular spectrum scanning operations. Consequently, the total computational complexity of the complete 3D-FFT imaging framework is expressed as:

$$C_{3D-FFT} = C_{cube} + C_{splice} + C_{wall} + C_{range} + C_{doppler} + C_{angle} \quad (68)$$

Substituting the dominant terms yields:

$$C_{3D-FFT} \approx \mathcal{O}(N_a N_p K I N_s \log N_s) \quad (69)$$

which indicates that the overall computational burden is still dominated by the iterative EMD clutter suppression stage. However, compared with MUSIC-based angle estimation, the FFT-based angular imaging framework offers substantially lower computational complexity and improved suitability for real-time TWRI implementation.

The 3D-FFT imaging framework introduces important tradeoffs between computational efficiency and angular estimation performance in TWRI systems. The primary advantage of the 3D-FFT framework lies in its substantially lower computational complexity. FFT operations exhibit efficient logarithmic scaling, and avoid computationally intensive operations. Consequently, the 3D-FFT approach is significantly more suitable for real-time TWRI implementation, particularly for large-scale radar datasets and resource-constrained embedded platforms. However, the angular resolution of 3D-FFT is fundamentally limited by the physical antenna aperture and FFT bin resolution. This leads to broader mainlobes and reduced capability to resolve closely spaced targets. In contrast,

Table 2: Computational complexity of 3D-FFT Based Imaging

Stage	Computational Cost
Data acquisition	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a)$
Channel splicing	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a)$
Wall clutter removal	$\Theta(K N_s N_p N_a)$
Range FFT	$\Theta(N_a N_p N_s \log N_s)$
Doppler FFT	$\Theta(N_a N_s N_p \log N_p)$
OS-CFAR	$\Theta(N_s N_p W \log W)$
Angle FFT	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a \log N_a)$

MUSIC provides super-resolution angle estimation and can distinguish multiple closely spaced targets beyond the classical Rayleigh resolution limit. MUSIC also generally offers higher angular estimation accuracy and better target separability in dense target environments. Nevertheless, these advantages are achieved at the expense of significantly increased computational burden. Moreover, MUSIC performance may degrade under low signal-to-noise ratio conditions and imperfect clutter suppression. Therefore, the 3D-FFT framework offers a computationally efficient and practically scalable solution, for real-time range-velocity-angle imaging. Whereas, MUSIC-based processing provides superior angular resolution and estimation accuracy for high-resolution TWRI applications, where computational resources are less constrained.

5.3 Computational Cost of RMA Based Imaging

The RMA based imaging framework begins with radar data acquisition and formation of the three-dimensional radar data cube. The received radar echoes are sampled across fast-time, slow-time, and spatial antenna dimensions, to formulate the radar data cube. Table 3 demonstrates the stepwise computational cost of TWRI using RMA approach. After radar cube formation, channel splicing is performed to concatenate the received data from all antenna channels into a unified observation matrix for spatial imaging. This operation mainly consists of memory rearrangement and indexing operations. Subsequently, wall clutter suppression is performed using iterative EMD algorithm. The EMD algorithm iteratively decomposes the received radar signals into multiple intrinsic mode functions through repeated extrema detection, spline interpolation, envelope estimation, and sifting operations.

Following clutter suppression, range FFT is applied along the fast-time dimension to transform the radar data into the range-frequency domain. For each antenna channel and slow-time sweep, an N_s -point FFT is computed. Since FFT complexity scales as $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$, the range FFT complexity becomes:

$$C_{range} = \mathcal{O}(N_a N_p N_s \log N_s) \quad (70)$$

This stage extracts target range information and converts the received radar signals into the wavenumber domain required for RMA processing. After range processing, Doppler FFT is performed along the slow-time dimension to estimate target velocity. For every range bin and antenna channel, an (N_p) – point FFT is computed. Therefore, the Doppler FFT computational complexity is expressed as :

$$C_{doppler} = \mathcal{O}(N_a N_s N_p \log N_p) \quad (71)$$

The range FFT and Doppler FFT stages jointly generate the range-Doppler representation required for subsequent RMA imaging. After Doppler processing, the RMA imaging chain performs spatial Fourier transformation along the antenna dimension to convert the radar data into the spatial wavenumber domain. This operation extracts angular spectral information across the antenna aperture. For every range-Doppler cell, an N_a -point FFT is computed across the antenna dimension. Hence, the spatial FFT complexity becomes:

$$C_{spatial} = \mathcal{O}(N_s N_p N_a \log N_a) \quad (72)$$

Following spatial FFT processing, the RMA algorithm performs matched filtering in the wavenumber domain. The matched filter compensates for phase propagation effects and focuses target reflections in the image domain. Since matched filtering involves element-wise complex multiplication across all data samples, the computational complexity scales linearly with the total dataset size:

$$C_{MF} = \mathcal{O}(N_s N_p N_a) \quad (73)$$

After matched filtering, Stolt interpolation is performed to compensate for range migration and remap the nonuniform wavenumber samples onto a uniform grid. Stolt interpolation is one of the most computationally intensive stages of RMA because interpolation must be independently performed for all range-Doppler-angle samples. Assuming interpolation complexity scales linearly with the total number of interpolated samples, the computational complexity becomes:

$$C_{Stolt} = \mathcal{O}(N_s N_p N_a) \quad (74)$$

Although the asymptotic order remains linear, Stolt interpolation introduces substantial practical computational overhead due to repeated interpolation and memory access operations. Finally, inverse multidimensional FFT is performed to reconstruct the focused radar image and estimate target range, velocity, and angle signatures. The inverse FFT operation is applied across the range, Doppler, and spatial dimensions. Therefore, the computational complexity of image reconstruction becomes:

$$C_{IFFT} = \mathcal{O}(N_s N_p N_a \log(N_s N_p N_a)) \quad (75)$$

This final stage reconstructs the focused three-dimensional TWRI image containing target range, velocity, and angular information. Consequently, the total computational complexity of the complete RMA imaging framework is expressed as:

$$C_{total} = C_{cube} + C_{splice} + C_{wall} + C_{range} + C_{doppler} + C_{spatial} + C_{MF} + C_{Stolt} + C_{IFFT} \quad (76)$$

Substituting the dominant terms yields:

$$C_{total} \approx \mathcal{O}(N_a N_p K I N_s \log N_s) \quad (77)$$

This indicates that iterative EMD clutter suppression remains the dominant computational stage. The second major computational contributors are inverse multidimensional FFT reconstruction, range FFT, and Doppler FFT operations. Compared with conventional 3D-FFT imaging, these operations in RMA increase the overall computational complexity and memory requirements.

Table 3: Computational complexity of RMA Based Imaging

Stage	Computational Cost
Data acquisition	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a)$
Channel splicing	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a)$
Wall clutter removal	$\Theta(K N_s N_p N_a)$
Range FFT	$\Theta(N_a N_p N_s \log N_s)$
Doppler FFT	$\Theta(N_a N_s N_p \log N_p)$
Spatial FFT	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a \log N_a)$
Matched Filtering	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a)$
Stolt Interpolation	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a)$
IFFT Reconstruction	$\Theta(N_s N_p N_a \log(N_s N_p N_a))$

The proposed FFT-MUSIC framework, conventional 3D-FFT imaging, and RMA-based imaging algorithms exhibit performance-critical tradeoffs, in terms of target parameter estimation accuracy, high-resolution imaging capability, and computational complexity for TWRI applications. The 3D-FFT framework offers the lowest computational complexity because all target signatures including range, velocity, and angle are estimated using efficient FFT operations with logarithmic computational scaling. This makes 3D-FFT highly suitable for real-time

implementation and hardware acceleration on FPGA or GPU platforms. However, its angular resolution is fundamentally constrained by antenna aperture size and FFT bin resolution, which limits its capability to resolve closely spaced targets and reduces angular estimation accuracy in dense target environments. On the other hand, the RMA-based imaging framework offers image focusing capability for range migration scenarios. Nevertheless, RMA encounters increased computational burden due to additional matched filtering, Stolt interpolation, multidimensional FFT reconstruction, and extensive memory operations.

The proposed high-resolution FFT-MUSIC imaging methodology provides an effective framework for accurate estimation of target signatures in complex TWRI environments. By combining FFT-based range-Doppler processing with subspace-based MUSIC angle estimation, the proposed framework achieves significantly improved parameter estimation accuracy and angular resolution. The subspace-based MUSIC processing introduces considerable computational burden due to covariance estimation, eigen-decomposition, and angular spectrum scanning operations. This challenge can be effectively addressed using modern FPGA and RFSoc platforms [46, 47]. Contemporary FPGA and RFSoc architectures provide massive parallel processing capability, dedicated DSP resources, and high-speed memory support for efficient implementation of matrix operations [48]-[50]. Therefore, the computational overhead of the proposed FFT-MUSIC framework can be substantially mitigated. This facilitates real-time high-resolution imaging for next-generation surveillance, electronic warfare, and indoor sensing applications.

6 Simulation Results and Analysis

6.1 Simulation Parameters

This section presents the simulation parameters and numerical results, along with comprehensive comparisons and extensive analysis. Table 4 presents the specifications of different simulation parameters. For CFAR detection, ordered-statistic (OS) algorithm is used with false-alarm probability of 1×10^{-6} . Moreover, 40 reference range cells are employed, and OS index $K = 25$ is chosen to mitigate the influence of outliers such as strong interfering targets or clutter edges.

6.2 Simulation Results

In order to validate the robustness of the proposed imaging framework and existing imaging schemes, two simulation scenarios are generated. Table III characterizes different parameters and specifications for both scenarios. In the first scenario, three targets are generated located at stand-off ranges 3, 10 and 12 m respectively. First and third targets are static and second one is moving away from the radar with velocity of 1 m/s. The azimuth angles of these targets are set to -10^0 , 10^0 and 20^0 respectively. In the second scenario, eight targets are

Table 4: Simulation Settings

Parameter	Specification
Sampling frequency	2 Msps
Center frequency	2 GHz
Bandwidth	500 MHz
Sweep time	500 μ s
Chirp rate	1 MHz/ μ s
Maximum range	20 m
System losses	6 dB
Wall losses	60 dB

generated located at stand-off ranges 5, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16 18 and 20 m respectively. First three targets are static, next three are moving away from the radar at 1 m/s, and last two are moving towards the radar at -1 m/s. The azimuth angles of these targets are set to -25^0 , -20^0 , -10^0 , 0^0 , 10^0 , 15^0 20^0 and 25^0 respectively.

Table 5: Simulated Environment Scenarios

Parameter	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
Number of targets	3	8
Targets range vector	{3, 10, 12} m	{5, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20} m
Targets velocity vector	{0, 1, 0} m/s	{0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, $-1, -1$ } m/s
Targets angle vector	$\{-10, 10, 20\}^0$	$\{-25, -20, -10, 0, 10, 15, 20, 25\}^0$
Targets RCS	$0.5 m^2$	$0.5 m^2$
Wall-Radar range	0.3 m	0.3 m

In order to capture a glimpse of RDM, Fig. 4 exhibits the range-velocity plot for the simulated scenario of eight targets, listed in Table II. It clearly points out 8 targets with their corresponding estimated velocity values. These results quantify substantial estimation accuracy even for large number of targets. Fig. 5 presents the plan position indicator (PPI) plots, to illustrate the performance of CBF for the two simulated scenarios. These results illustrate multiple smeared or overlapping responses at the same range bins, indicating poor angular discrimination. This is a direct consequence of its relatively broad mainlobe and

high sidelobe levels. As a result, multiple targets located within or near the same beamwidth appear as a single merged or ambiguous response. This highlights a key performance limitation of CBF in high-resolution radar imaging, especially when precise angular separation is required in cluttered or multi-target environments.

Fig. 4: Illustration of RDM for eight targets (Scenario 2)

Fig. 6 presents the range-azimuth maps to evaluate the performance of different image reconstruction (IR) algorithms, for the case of three targets. The parameters and specifications of these three targets are listed in Table II. It is quite evident from these range-angle maps that FT-ES-MUSIC based algorithm outperforms the other approaches in terms of focused image reconstruction and estimation accuracy. Similarly, Fig. 7 demonstrates a more complicated scenario of eight targets, specified in Table III. The range-angle maps clearly indicate that the proposed hybrid (HIR) scheme achieves superior estimation accuracy compared to other approaches. These results validate the robustness of proposed methodology, even for significant number of targets.

It has already been demonstrated that both CBF and RMA fail to resolve multiple targets in the azimuth direction. Fig. 8 depicts the accuracy of angle estimation in terms of root mean square error (RMSE), across a wide angle sweep -40° to 40° . It represents a comparative analysis of angle estimation accuracy at different target ranges, over 100 Monte Carlo iterations. Overall, the comparison underscores the dependence of angle estimation accuracy on target range. Table IV summarizes the estimation accuracy of target parameters i.e., range, velocity

Fig. 5: CBF performance (a) Three targets scenario (b) Eight targets scenario

and angle, for eight targets (Scenario 2 in Table III) over 100 Monte Carlo iterations.

Table 6: Parameters Estimation Accuracy

Algorithm	Range	Velocity	Angle
Proposed HIR	89 %	89 %	89.75 %
FT-IR	88 %	88 %	71.5 %
RMA-IR	85 %	79 %	49.25 %
CBF	83 %	77.5 %	49 %

7 Conclusion

This paper presents high-resolution hybrid imaging framework for FMCW based through-the-wall MIMO radar systems. As electronic warfare continues to evolve toward information dominance and precision engagement, TWRI stands out as a key enabling technology for intelligence gathering, threat detection, and mission planning in complex operational environments. TWRI faces significant challenges due to wall-induced distortion, multipath propagation, and clutter, which degrade image quality and target localization accuracy. To address these issues, the proposed framework exploits the concept of virtual array to enhance spatial resolution. A robust TWRI chain is developed based on Fourier transform and subspace-based hybrid image reconstruction (HIR) methodology for TWRI scenario. Moreover, a comprehensive analytical model is formulated for the proposed imaging scheme, alongwith mathematical derivations. A comprehensive computational complexity analysis is performed for each algorithm, con-

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6: Three targets scenario (a) RMA-IR (b) FT-IR (c) FT-ES-MUSIC-IR

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7: Eight targets scenario (a) RMA-IR (b) FT-IR (c) FT-ES-MUSIC-IR

Fig. 8: RMSE of estimated azimuth angle

firming the efficiency and scalability of the proposed approach in real-world TWR applications. Furthermore, extensive simulations and comparisons are conducted under various multi-target conditions to evaluate the performance of each method. Numerical results demonstrate that the proposed methodology achieves superior accuracy in terms of targets detection and parameters estimation. The 3D-FFT framework offers the lowest computational complexity because all target signatures including range, velocity, and angle are estimated using efficient FFT operations with logarithmic computational scaling. The proposed high-resolution FFT-MUSIC imaging methodology offers higher angular estimation accuracy and target resolution in dense target environments. In the light of modern resources-rich hardware platforms, it provides an effective and practical framework for accurate estimation of target signatures in complex TWRI environments.

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